

BONFIGLIOLI L., URBANAVIČIŪTĖ I., PAGNOTTA M. A.

Department of Agricultural and Forest Sciences, Tuscia University, via S. C. de Lellis snc, 01100 Viterbo, Italy

ABSTRACT

Durum wheat adaptation to drought stress would ensure food security in most of the Mediterranean countries. Abiotic stresses have a significant impact on durum wheat cultivation, with a registered loss of production up to 72% and 40% for drought and salinity, respectively. In addition, the demand of organic food, as well as healthy food, is increasing. However, there is still a lack of stable and high-yielding crop varieties specifically adapted for organic conditions and tolerant to abiotic stresses. In order to characterize accession with different drought tolerance, genotypic and phenotypic approaches were used. Fifteen durum wheat accessions potentially suitable for organic agriculture were evaluated in field experiments over four successive seasons which were characterized by contrasting thermo-pluviometric values. The impact of the genotype-environment interaction (G×E) on productive and quality traits is an important parameter in selecting accession suitable for climatic changes. In addition, a genotypic diversity analysis of 38 microsatellites associated with traits important for organic farming and tolerance to abiotic stresses was performed. G×E in conjunction with molecular analyses can improve durum wheat selection and breeding. We identified stable and high-yielding accessions with either high or stable-quality parameters. In addition, the used markers were identified as suitable for stable and high yield selection, as well as meeting quality parameters under organic farming conditions. The present work was conducted in the frame of the ECOBREED project (European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 771367).

MATERIALS & METHODS

Fifteen accessions (Table 1) was evaluated in a four-year experiment, it was performed at the experimental farm at Tuscia University located in Viterbo, Italy using a RBD with three replications. The durum wheat screening focused mainly on traits important to organic farming, i.e. ground cover (GC), growth habit (GH), days to heading (HD), grain yield (GY), test or hectoliter weight (HLW), protein content (PROT), and thousand-kernel weight (TKG).

Table 1. Origin and Pedigree of durum wheat varieties.

Lines	Origin	Pedigree
Azeghar2-1(56)	ICARDA, Syr	Selection from AZEGHAR2: 20048Traikia(Mor)/Mrb5//Stj3
Sebatel2-45	ICARDA, Syr	Selection from Sebatel-2//Wdz6/Gil4 (ICD02-.....-0AP)
Icajin 38(64)	ICARDA, Syr	Selection from Icajihan1 (ICD01-0251-T-4AP-TR-1AP-0AP)
Mv-Makaroni	Hungary	Selected from MTA-ATK Martonvasar (HU) crosses
Mv-Pelsodur	Hungary	Selected from MTA-ATK Martonvasar (HU) crosses
MVTD15-19	Hungary	Selected from MTA-ATK Martonvasar (HU) crosses
MVTD20-19	Hungary	Selected from MTA-ATK Martonvasar (HU) crosses
Mv-Vekadur	Hungary	Selected from MTA-ATK Martonvasar (HU) crosses
Iride	Italy	Altar 84/Ares (= Ionio)
Saragolla	Italy	Iride/Linea PSB 0114 PBS
Cappelli	Italy	Selection from North African landraces Jennah Khetifa
Vulci	MA	Varieties released by Syngenta Company in the Mediterranean area
Fuego	MA	Varieties released by Syngenta Company in the Mediterranean area
Gibraltar	MA	Varieties released by Syngenta Company in the Mediterranean area
HFN 94n	Unknown origin	

The test weight (kg/hL) and protein (%) were analyzed using NIR spectroscopy analysis. To assess the genotypic diversity, 38 microsatellites associated with traits important for organic farming, i.e., 8 for biotic stress, 7 related to yield and quality traits, 10 root-related traits, and 13 for heading day and shoot length (Table 2), were chosen.

Table 2. Co-dominant SSR markers associated with traits important for organic farming.

Biotic stress	Chr.	Marker	Biotic stress	Chr.	Marker
Powdery Mildew	5BL	wmc75	Primary Root Length	2AS	gwm636
Leaf Rust	1B	gwm18	Root Angle	5A	wms205
Leaf Rust	1B	Xbarc187	Total Seminal Root Length	7AL	cfa2257
Fusarium	7A	gwm282	Primary Root Length	5AL	wmc727
Powdery Mildew	5BL	gpw7425	Root Angle	4al	gwm637
Leaf Rust	7B	barc340	Root Angle	6AS	gwm459
Fusarium	3B	barc133	Root Angle	6A	gwm427
Pyrenophora Tritici-repentis (Died.)	3B	gwm285	Root Angle - Gpc	5BL	gwm499
Yield And Quality			Shoot Length - Heading Day		
Grain Protein Content - TKW	5AS	barc117	Flowering time (Vrn-B1)	5B	Xgwm408
Grain Weight	1B	Xgwm413	Heading day	3BS	Xgwm389
Grain Weight	1B	Xgwm413	Heading day	2AL	cfa2086
Grain Protein Content	3BS	barc147	Heading day	3BS	gwm566
Grain Protein Content - GY	3BS	wms493	Heading day	1AL	gwm99
Grain Protein Content	4AL	barc170	Heading day	7AS/7BS	gwm573.2
Sedimentation Index	1BL	cfa2129	Shoot length	3AS/3BS	wmc505.1
Root Traits			Shoot length/RDW/SDW (mg)	6BL	Xbarc134
Root Angle	3AS	wms5	Shoot length/RDW/TRL (cm)	3AL	gwm155
ROOT ANGLE - Dough Strenght	5BS	gwm234	shoot length - Heading Day	7BL	Xgwm46
			Shoot length	2A/2B	Xcfd50
			Shoot length	5BL	gwm213
			Shoot length	7AL	gwm332

RESULTS

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed a significant genotype (G) effect for all traits. In addition, a significant GEI for traits such as grain yield (GY), test weight (HLW), protein content (PROT), and thousand-kernel weight (TKG) were obtained (Table 3). The heading day (HD), ground cover (GC), and growth habit (GH) did not show significant GEI, accordingly.

Table 3. ANOVA significance of agronomical, yield, and quality parameters of 15 durum wheat genotypes over four growing seasons.

Source of Variance	df	HD	GY	HLW	TKG	PROT	GC	GH
(E)	3	p < 0.001	0.321	p < 0.001	p < 0.001	p < 0.001	0.013	p < 0.001
(G)	14	p < 0.001	0.01	p < 0.001				
GEI	42	0.137	p < 0.01	p < 0.001	p < 0.001	p < 0.001	0.186	0.176

Figure 1. Additive main effects and multiplicative interaction (AMMI 1) biplots show the GEI of the 15 durum wheat varieties under 4 environments for (A) thousand-kernel weight (TKW), (B) test weight (HLW), (C) grain yield (GY) and (D) protein content (PROT).

CONCLUSIONS

The combination of GEI analysis and SSR markers can improve durum wheat selection and breeding. Our investigated genotype analysis indicated that we could provide information about either stable and high-yielding varieties, such as Fuego, Iride, and Mv-Pelsodur, or Senatore Cappelli with high and stable quality parameters, but not both in a single genotype. However, 12 SSR markers were identified as suitable for durum wheat selection for stable and high yields, as well as meeting quality parameters under organic farming conditions. In addition, the determined genotypes can be useful candidate parental lines for breeding new varieties suitable for organic agriculture, characterized by stable, high yield, and quality parameters.